

Survey, Detection and Incidence of Seed-borne Mycoflora on *Chrysanthemum parthenium* Seeds

Paper Id : 19801 Submission Date : 2025-01-08 Acceptance Date : 2025-01-21 Publication Date : 2025-01-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14910254

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Abstract

Floriculture is an important branch of horticulture is gaining popularity as an industry for earning foreign exchange [Rao ,1991]. *Chrysanthemum parthenium* belongs to the family "Asteraceae". In Rajasthan commercial cultivation of *Chrysanthemum parthenium* is for worship and garland making. The plant also cultivated as medicinal plant and used as insecticide and vermifuge [Olg and Polunin, 1969]. The plant is suffering from many fungal and bacterial diseases. A total 80 seed samples of *chrysanthemum* were collected from 11 district of Rajasthan Viz. Ajmer, Banswara, Bharatpur, Dausa, Jaipur, Karauli, Kishangarh, Kota, Sikar, Tonk and Udaipur and categorized in to asymptomatic and symptomatic seeds with various disorders. All the seed samples of chrysanthemum were screened by SBM and PDA. 30 fungal species of 18 genera were dissociated in SBM and 25 fungal species belonging to 16 genera were recorded on PDA. The mycoflora were *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *F. moniliforme*, *Dreschlera halodes*, *Curvuleria lunata*, *Alternata solanai*, *A. tenuissima*, *Aspergillus candidus*, *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus*, *Arthrotrichum superba*, *cercospora species*, *Cheatomium spinosum*, *Cladosporium cladosporoides*, *F.semitectum* and *Penicillium sp.* Present work done mainly on *A. alternata* and *F.moniliforme*.

Keywords Chrysanthemum parthenium, Mycoflora, SBM, PDA, Symptomatic.

Introduction

Chrysanthemum parthenium [L.] Benth is widely grown in Rajasthan and other part of the country. It is perennial plant with daisy like flower heads 2.5 cm in size with yellow disc and ray florets. It is suitable for border edging [Berickell, 1996]. In Rajasthan flowers are widely uses for garland making. *Chrysanthemum parthenium* is a native of Europe [Bhattacharjee, 2005]. Higher light intensities and high temperature encourage vegetative growth of chrysanthemum [Chadha and Chaudhary, 1986]. They are propagated by seeds and cutting of plants. Leaves are used for bad colds indication and diarrhoea. Dried flowers are used to induce menstrual flow and bring about abortion. Leaves are chewed to relieve colic [Bhattacharjee, 2005].

Objective of study The study was performed on crop seeds collected from different regions of Rajasthan. It was identified in the study that many types of fungus were present on the symptomatic crop seeds. Out of which, the incidence of 2 types of fungus was the highest.

Review of Literature

Micropropagation of plants to generate large scale of flowers for pyrethrin extraction (Catalano Et. Al.), 2022.

Chrysanthemum parthenium suffers from many fungal and bacterial diseases. The major diseases are powdery mildew [*Erysiphae chichoraciarum*], root and stem rot[*Rhizoctonia solani*], fruit rot [*Colletotrichum gleosporioides*], blight [*Corticium salmoniador*], leaf spot [*Ascochyta caricae*, *Alternaria* sp.], flower rot [*Alternaria tanuis* and *Aspergillus niger*] [Westcott,1971]. The seed botanically a cypcella fruit . The description of the structure of normal seed is based on the observation of present study as well as on the brief description of Asteraceae seed provided by[Vaughan,1970].

Methodology

Dry Seed Examination

All the collected seeds samples of chrysanthemum from eleven district of Rajasthan were stocked in polythene bag individually and given an accession number .The packets were stored in dry condition. For dry seeds examination 400 seeds per sample were taken randomly and analyzed by naked eyes as well as under stereoscopic binocular microscope (10-40X). Seeds were identified as asymptomatic (healthy looking) and symptomatic seeds. Symptoms showed as seeds discolourations, shriveled and small size seeds.

35 Seed samples carried black discolouration on seed surface and percentage occurrence was 0.75 -10.25%. 42 samples contained brown discoloured seeds and incidence was 1.0 - 17.25%. 22 seeds samples carried 0.75 – 3.75% shriveled seeds. Small size seeds were recorded 1.0 – 5.0%. Seeds with shiny appearance had smooth surface and ranging from 0.25 - 2.5% only recorded in three districts.

Incubation Test

For incubation test Standard Blotter Method (SBM) and Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plate method applied, seed health testing procedure as prescribed by International Seed Testing Association were followed. 80 seeds were treated with aqueous soln. of sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) with 1, 2, 2.5, 3 and 4% for 1, 2, 3 and 5 min. treatment with 2.0% hypochlorite solution was most effective for surface sterilization of seeds and the NaOCl remove surface mycoflora without affecting the seed germination. Untreated seeds were washed only with distilled water. 20 seeds per plate were placed in sterilized Petri plates containing 3 wet blotter paper which are incubated at $25^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ} \text{c}$. Alternate cycles of light and darkness provides (12/12hrs.) On 8th day of incubation, percentage of seed germination, seed-borne mycoflora, seedling symptoms were recorded and RPO was calculated. 41seeds samples were studied by PDA method in which 200 sterilized seeds were placed in sterile condition on Petri plates containing 15-20 ml (PDA) medium (20 seeds/plates) and incubated at $25^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ} \text{c}$ in 12hrs.alternating cycles of light and darkness for 7 days. Incidence of fungus and seeds germination were recorded.

TABLE : INCIDENCE, RELATIVE PERCENT OCCURRENCE (RPO) AND PERCENT RANGE OF FUNGI

IN CHLORINE PRETREATED SEEDS OF CHRYSANTHEMUM SBM AND PDA TESTS:

FUNGI	SBM			PDA		
	Incidence	RPO	% range of Fungi	Incidence	RPO	% range of Fungi
<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	32	40.00	1--42	24	58.53	1--24
<i>A. linicola</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. solani</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A.tenuissima</i>	6	7.50	1.3	7	17.07	1--4
<i>Arthrotrrys superba</i>	10	12.50	1--10	8	19.5	1--9
<i>Aspergillus candidus</i>	4	5.00	1--3	5	12.19	1--5
<i>A. flavus</i>	8	10.00	1--5	6	41.46	1--20
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	6	7.50	1--3	3	7.31	1--4
<i>A.niger</i>	3	3.75	1--2	1	2.43	2
<i>A. versicolor</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Cercospora sp.</i>	6	7.50	1--3	5	12.19	1--2
<i>Cephalosporium sp.</i>	4	5.00	1--2	2	4.87	1, 3
<i>Chaetomidium fimeti</i>	2	1.88	1, 3	3	7.31	1--2
<i>C. globosum</i>	8	10.00	1--6	4	9.75	1--8
<i>C. spinosum</i>	-	-	-	5	12.19	1--2
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	5	6.25	1--2	2	4.87	2, 3
<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	9	11.25	1--8	4	9.75	1--3
<i>Drechslera holodes</i>	2	1.88	2, 4	1	2.43	2
<i>Fusarium equiseti</i>	2	1.88	1, 3	-	-	-
<i>F. moniliforme</i>	30	37.50	1--40	21	51.21	1--45
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	7	8.75	1--10	4	9.75	1--15
<i>F. semitectum</i>	4	5.00	1--5	2	4.87	1, 2
<i>Penicillium sp.</i>	5	6.25	1--6	2	4.87	1, 5
<i>Periconia spp.</i>	-	-	-	3	7.31	1--2
<i>Phthophthora parasitica</i>	3	3.75	1--4	2	4.87	1, 2
<i>Rhizctonia solani</i>	3	3.75	1--9	3	7.31	1--2
<i>Rhizopus nigricanse</i>	4	5.00	1--5	3	7.31	1--2
<i>Stachybotrys atra</i>	5	6.25	1--2	2	4.87	1--2
<i>Rrichothicium rosium</i>	2	1.88	1, 3	-	-	-
<i>Verticillium alboatrum</i>	2	1.88	1, 2	-	-	-

Dry seed examination and growth of pathogen on seed

A – Healthy (left), Black discoloured seeds (right) by *Alternaria alternata* by 15x

B – Growth of pathogen on seed surface on blotter method

C,D – Component plating showing growth of pathogen on seed coat (C) and Cotyledon (D) 6.6x, 12x

E – Cleared wholemound preparation showing mycelium of pathogen in seed coat

Result and Discussion

Neergaard (1977) has described the 3 basic categories of seeds discolouration viz. Superficial narcotic lesions, fungal coating and pigmentation. The present study concern with healthy looking seeds, brown to black discolouration, small sized and shiny seeds. Black discolouration of seeds constituted primarily with *Alternaria alternata* on SBM. Similar result observed by Kumar and Singh (2005) on pigeon pea caused by *Alternaria tenuissima*. In present study percent range of *A.alternata* was recorded 1-42% in sterilized seeds (SBM) and 1-24% in PDA (table). Occurrences of the pathogen carried from 1– 75% in untreated seeds. Infection of *Fusarium moniliforme* established and appeared as brown discolouration on seed surface. Similar observation were recorded by Agarwal (2000) in Okra seeds caused by *F.oxysporum*, radish brown in soyabean. Mathur (1992). Percent incidence was obtained (1-40%) in pretreated seeds on SBM, (1-45%) on PDA (table) as compared to untreated seeds(1-68%) on SBM. Robinson (1963) isolated *Ramularia bellunensis* from *chrysanthemum parthenium*, Cox (1969) observed *Alternaria solani*, *A.tenuis* and *stemphyllum* sp. Associated with *chrysanthemum* seeds. Westcott (1971) recorded *Erysiphe cichoracearum*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Colletotrichum gliosporioides*, *Corticium salmoniedor*, *Alternaria* sp., *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis* (*A.alternata*) and *Botrytis cinerea* on seeds of *chrysanthemum parthenium*.

Conclusion

In present study *Alternaria alternata*, *A.tenuissima*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *A.fumigatus*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *F.oxysporum*, *Curvuleria lunata*, *Rhizopus nigricanse* and *Phytophthora* the important fungi isolated as causing pre and post emergence losses. Out of these *Alternaria alternata* and *Fusarium moniliforme* depicted maximum seed infection. Both were sustained with maximum percentage on SBM and PDA as compared to other fungi. Both pathogen were produced symptomatic seedlings with higher intensities/percentage and showed loss in seed germination. Dissociation of both fungus was higher as related to other fungus indicated seed-borne nature of *A.alternata* and *F.moniliforme*. *A.alternata* has been reported to be seed borne in

sunflower(Singh, Mathur & Neergaard, 1977), Pot marigold (Shrotri, Gupta and Srivastava, 1985), Soyabean (Kunwar, Manandhar and Sinclais, 1986), Wheat (Agarwal, Sharma, Singh and Singh, 1987), plants of family to Asteraceae(Prasad, 1987). A wilt of chrysanthemum in nursery beds of Lucknow caused by *F.oxysporum* identified by Ghosh and Singh(1982), *F.moniliforme* to cause ovule rot of sago palm (Prasad, Aneja, Shanker and Navneet,1992).

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